

Strategic Effects of Woman Fans on Football Matches¹

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ABSTRACT

With the slogan of "Beautiful game will stay beautiful", the Turkish Football Federation designed a project to be implemented in the 2011-2012 season, for enabling "Women and children under 12 years of age to go to matches free of charge", with intent to make contributions to the future of football, increase interest, prevent violence and disorder, dissuade ugly and bad cheering, and create an atmosphere enabling families to easily watch events.

Allowing only women and children to watch the matches, which have been ordered by the Turkish Football Federation to be played without spectators in the 2011-2012 Season, began with Fenerbahce's home match against Manisaspor. It was thought, said and written by the public opinion that Sukru Saracoglu Stadium would not be able to be filled up in any way; and that maximum 5-10 thousand spectators would attend the Fenerbahce-Manisa match played on September 20, 2011. However, a first was experienced in the spectator history of the world, and Sukru Saracoglu stadium was packed with 41,663 women and children.

In 2011-2012 football season, eight matches were played in the Super League, with the attendance of women and children fans. Our study is intended for ascertaining whether women and children spectators have positive effects on matches. In this context, the numbers of yellow cards, red cards, goals and match results of the matches played with women and children fans were compared with that of the matches played between the same teams in the same season. It was tried to determine if the spectators were effective on the numbers of yellow cards, red cards, goals and match results, during the matches attended by women and children fans.

As a result, we can say that less yellow cards are shown in the matches played with the attendance of women and children fans, and consequently, matches are played in a more sportsmanlike environment and in accordance with the principles of Fair Play. Mass violence events are not observed in or around of stadiums, for the matches attended by women and children fans. Football will obtain a new visage with the new fans it gained/will gain. Preventing violence and disorder, dissuading ugly and bad cheering, and creating an atmosphere that enables families to easily watch events will enable football to reach the desirable level, and beauties in a shorter time. Women should not exist only in stadiums but also everywhere related to football...

Keywords: Football, Woman fan, Fair Play

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INTRODUCTION

With the slogan of "Beautiful game will stay beautiful", a project to be implemented in the 2011-2012 season was commenced, for enabling "Women and children under 12 years of age to go to matches free of charge", with intent to make contributions to the future of football, increase interest, prevent violence and disorder, dissuade ugly and bad cheering, and create an atmosphere enabling families to easily watch events (TFF, 2011a).

The project of the Turkish Football Federation enabling "Women and children under 12 years of age to go to matches free of charge" was put into practice with the Fenerbahce - Manisaspor match, as one of the Sports Toto Super League matches, played on September 20. After this decision of the Turkish Football Federation, the "penalties of playing without spectators" were wanted to be turned into free match watching feasts for women and children (TFF, 2011a).

Article 32 of the section "Disciplinary Punishments" in the Football Disciplinary Regulations is about the "penalty of playing without spectators". Before the Football Federation's decision about women, this penalty had been a type of penalty criticized by all the football society, and a consensus had been reached on standing

out against playing without spectators. Also bringing women to stadiums was considered and desired for our football but the implementation of that required some measures to be taken and some projects to be designed. With its decision, the Turkish Football Federation wanted to combine two negative situations to reach a positive result. Accordingly, the matches would not be played without spectator, and on the other hand, women would attend the matches (TFF, 2011b).

It was thought, said and written that Sukru Saracoglu Stadium would not be able to be filled up in any way; and that maximum 5-10 thousand spectators would attend the Fenerbahce-Manisa match played in September 20, 2011. However, a first was experienced in the spectator history of the world, and Sukru Saracoglu stadium was packed with 41,663 women and children for the Fenerbahce-Manisa match (Hurriyet, 2011).

When they were given opportunity, Fenerbahce's women fans showed the fact that football and the love of football do not belong to only men; and showed also how much they were modern. In addition, with that match the football industry noticed the women fans and made its products suitable for women. The products with logo purchased by Fenerbahce's women fans in Manisa and Sivas match lead to 25 percent increase in the sales of women's and children's clothing products, by constituting the 25 percent of total turnover. Thus, the importance of the women spectators in the Turkish football industry came into view (Haberturk, 2012).

As the first match played with women and children spectators in Turkey Super League, Fenerbahce Manisa match was followed by the matches of Bursa-Galatasaray, Ankaragucu-Trabzon, Besiktas-Mersin Idman Yurdu, Fenerbahce-Sivas, Bursa-K. Karabuk, Besiktas-Trabzon and Bursaspor-Fenerbahce (Orta, 2012a).

Nice Fair Play examples were experienced in Besiktas-Trabzonspor match played with the attendance of Women and children. Besiktas-Trabzonspor match was watched by 21 thousand women and children fans. Inonu Stadium turned into a carnival place, with the cheers and scarf shows of the women and children. Trabzonspor's women and children fans showed great interest in the event, and packed the place with the capacity of 1,600 people, which was allocated for them. Besiktas's women fans showed an example of "sportsmanlike fans" by applauding Trabzon's fans. It was a nice Fair Play example that a fan of Besiktas requested and received the uniform of a Trabzonspor player. (Orta, 2012b).

After a position in Bursaspor-Galatasaray match, the women fans reacted by using bad language against the referee in a collective manner, and two women fans came to blows after Beşiktaş-Trabzonspor match.

The women fans' reaction in the form of using bad language against the referee after a position in Bursaspor-Galatasaray match can be identified with the fact that they were just introduced to the spirit of Fair Play; and can be considered as the trace that the men fans in Turkey left in their subconscious for years. The incident of the two women fans, who came to blows after Beşiktaş-Trabzonspor match, must be considered as an individual case, and it must not be able to overshadow the beauties experienced during the match (Orta, 2012b).

For those who give these one or two individual cases as example and allege that nothing changed in the matches attended by women fans, it is useful to reminding some of the acts of violence experienced in the matches attended by mostly men spectators.

Some of the Acts of Violence in the Turkish Football

The greatest violence catastrophe suffered by our country in football was experienced in the minor league match played in September 1967 between Kayserispor and Sivasspor. 48 people were killed and 600 people were injured in a brawl between the fans of the two teams, and the tribunes of the stadium were burned and destroyed (Hurriyet, 2000).

During a Turkish 3rd League match between Mardin and Kars Rural Services, the president of Mardinspor fired five gunshots and ran after the rival players in the field (Türker, 1992).

Besiktas's fans became hysterical over their team's limping out of the Turkey Cup, and the hooligans who attacked the Kocaelispor fans stabbed a young man (Bel, 1997).

Successive acts of violence were experienced in the Turkish football. A lynching attempt was made to the football player Ogun; The football coach Mustafa Denizli was attacked; Besiktas's Manager Ilker Özbilek was slapped in the face by a fan (Hurriyet, 1997).

The father who shot and killed his son while he was celebrating the victory of the national match in Adana by firing his gun into the air become a killer (Görgün, 1997).

The man who warned the young people commenting on the match in a coffeehouse were killed by a hunting rifle (Anar, 1998).

There were uncivilized scenes in Trabzonspor stadium (Star, 1999)

The journalists Fatih Altayli was injured in the head and hand, in consequence of the events arisen in the protocol tribune after the Galatasaray-Fenerbahce match (Sabah, 2003).

The fans who fought tooth and claw during Goztepe-Izmir match, turned Izmir Alsancak stadium into hell. The KSK fan Murat Kongu, who was stabbed in his 4 locations, could not be saved from death (Vatan, 2003).

The little girl Busra, who was injured in her head by a stone, threw during the Trabzonspor-Fenerbahce match, said; do not let any other brother or sister get injured" (Star, 2003)

The former referee and sports commentator Dr. Ahmet Cakar was assaulted by someone with a gun (Atakol, 2004).

Besiktas' and Bursaspor's fans came to blow before the match started. The police used pepper gas during the fight, in which sticks and stones were used by the fans (Milliyet, 2010).

The Bursaspor-Besiktas match was canceled due to the events that took place around the stadium before the match (Hurriyet, 2011).

The implementation commenced with intent to make contribution to the studies carried out in Turkey to prevent violence was decided to be prolonged for once more season. Allowing only women and children under 12 years of age to watch the matches, which have been ordered by the Turkish Football Federation to be played without spectators, was decided to be continued in 2012-2013 as well. Accordingly, women and children under 12 years of age will continue to enter the stadiums for watching the matches which have been subjected to the penalty of playing without spectators. If in the matches watched by women and children free of charge the disciplinary committees decided to give the penalty of playing without spectators or stadium ban due to events in the stadium, the decision of allowing women and children to enter the stadium will not be implemented for the relevant football team. Similarly, if in the matches watched by women and children free of charge the disciplinary committees decides to apply disciplinary sanction due to ugly and bad cheering two times a season, any spectators will not be allowed to enter the stadium, excluding those who enter the protocol tribune, for the home matches to be played without spectators (TFF, 2012).

METHOD

Our study was carried out to make a general review intended for ascertaining whether women and children spectators have positive effects on matches during the football season. In this context, the following data were utilized for the eight matches played in the Turkish Super League during the 2011-2012 football season, with the attendance of women and children:

- Numbers of yellow cards
- Numbers of red cards
- Numbers of goals scored
- Match results

In the football season, the numbers of yellow cards, red cards, goals and match results of the matches played with women and children fans were compared with that of the matches played between the same teams in the same season. Accordingly, the numbers of yellow cards, red cards, goals and match results will be examined, the matches will be compared, and it will be determined if there is any difference between the numbers of yellow cards, red cards, goals and match results.

FINDINGS

Allowing women and children to watch the matches free of charge began with Fenerbahçe-Manisaspor match played on September 20, 2011, and eight matches played in the Super League, with the attendance of women and children. These matches are the followings:

- Fenerbahçe - Manisaspor
- Bursaspor – Galatasaray
- Ankaragücü – Trabzonspor
- Beşiktaş – Mersin İdman Yurdu
- Fenerbahçe – Sivasspor
- Bursaspor – Kardemir Karabükspor
- Beşiktaş – Trabzonspor
- Fenerbahçe – Bursaspor

The following data were used in our study carried out to make a general review intended for ascertaining whether women and children spectators have positive effects on matches during the football season.

- Numbers of yellow cards
- Numbers of red cards
- Numbers of goals scored
- Match results

The numbers of yellow cards, red cards, goals and match results of these matches were determined, and they were compared with that of the other matches played between the same teams. The data regarding the numbers of yellow cards, red cards, and goals of the matches played with the attendance of women and children spectators are shown in Table 1 and Figure 1.

Table 1: Matches played with Women's and Children's spectators in Super League

Date	Matches	Results	Yellow Cards	Red Cards	The Number of Goals
20.09.2011	Fenerbahçe-Manisa	1-1	1+2=3	0+1=1	2
29.01.2012	Bursa-Galatasaray	1-0	3+1=4	-	1
29.01.2012	Ankaragücü-Trabzon	0-4	2+3=5	-	4
02.02.2012	Beşiktaş-M.İ.Yurdu	0-1	2+2=4	1+0=1	1
18.02.2012	Fenerbahçe-Sivas	4-2	1+4=5	-	6
04.03.2012	Bursa-K.Karabük	3-0	0+3=3	-	3
04.03.2012	Beşiktaş-Trabzon	1-2	4+3=7	-	3
24.03.2012	Fenerbahçe-Bursa	1-0	0+1=1	-	1
Total			32	2	21

Figure 1: Matches played with Women's and Children's Spectators in Super League (The numbers of yellow cards, red cards, goals)

In the football season, the numbers of yellow cards, red cards, goals and match results of the matches played with women and children fans as well as that of the matches played between the same teams in the same season are shown in Table 2 and Figure 2.

Table 2: 2011-2012 Football Season with each Other the Same Teams Played Other Matches

Date	Matches	Results	Yellow Cards	Red Cards	The Number of Goals
16.01.2011	Manisa-Fenerbahçe	1-2	1+2=3	-	3
16.10.2011	Galatasaray-Bursa	2-1	4+3=7	-	3
14.10.2011	Trabzon-Ankaragücü	3-2	2+3=5	-	5
24.10.2011	M.İ.Yurdu-Beşiktaş	0-1	3+3=6	-	1
04.11.2011	Sivas-Fenerbahçe	2-0	2+2=4	-	2
27.11.2011	K.Karabük-Bursa	3-1	6+1=7	-	4
27.11.2011	Trabzon-Beşiktaş	0-1	2+2=4	1+0=1	1
12.12.2011	Bursa-Fenerbahçe	0-2	4+3=7	-	2
Total			43	1	21

Figure 2: 2011-2012 Football Season with each Other the Same Teams Played Other Matches (The numbers of yellow cards, red cards, goals)

Among the eight matches played in the Super League with women and children, only Fenerbahçe-Manisaspor match resulted in a draw, and four matches won by the home teams while three matches won by the visiting teams. Ankaragücü is the only team that played home match with women and children, apart from Besiktas, Bursaspor and Fenerbahçe.

Fenerbahçe achieved two wins and a draw from the three league matches that it played with women and children fans. Bursaspor won the two home matches and lost a match that it played away. Besiktas lost the two home matches, while Trabzonspor won the two matches that it played away.

When we compare the eight matches played with women and children fans and the other eight matches played with the same teams, any difference is not seen between the totals of the numbers of red cards and goal scores (Figure 3 and Figure 4).

Figure 3: 2011-2012 Football Season with Women's and Children's Spectators in Super League and with each Other the Same Teams Played Other Matches (The numbers of red cards)

Figure 4: 2011-2012 Football Season with Women's and Children's Spectators in Super League and with each Other the Same Teams Played Other Matches (The numbers of goals)

There is not a significant difference in the total number of yellow card (Figure 5). The number of yellow cards shown in the matches watched by women and children fans was lesser up to 11. Since the red card shown in the Fenerbahçe-Manisaspor match was shown as a result of the second yellow card, we can consider this difference as 9.

Figure 5. 2011-2012 Football Season with Women's and Children's Spectators in Super League and with each Other the Same Teams Played Other Matches (The numbers of yellow cards)

According to the Laws of the Game of the FIFA, the violations leading a player to be shown a yellow card are as follows:

- 1- If he/she is guilty of an unsporting behavior,
- 2- If he/she objects to the referee's or referees' decisions, with word or action,
- 3- If he/she persistently infringes on the rules of the game,
- 4- If he/she delays the resumption of the game,
- 5- If he/she fails to respect the required distance when play is restarted with a corner kick, free kick or throw-in,
- 6- If he/she enters or re-enters the field of play without the referee's permission,
- 7- If he/she deliberately leaves the field of play without the referee's permission (FIFA, 2012).

CONCLUSION AND EVALUATION

Mass violence events are not observed in or around of stadiums, for the matches attended by women and children fans. Football will obtain a new visage with the new fans it gained/will gain. Preventing violence and disorder, dissuading ugly and bad cheering, and creating an atmosphere that enables families to easily watch events will enable football to reach the desirable level, and beauties in a shorter time. Women should not exist only in stadiums but also everywhere related to football..

Allowing women and children to watch the matches, which have been ordered by the Turkish Football Federation to be played without spectators, was evaluated by the UEFA President Michel Platini by saying "that is a great idea".

When we compare the eight matches played with women and children fans and the other eight matches played with the same teams, any difference is not seen between the totals of the numbers of red cards and goal scores. It is understood that whether the spectators are women, men or children is not a factor that has an effect on the performances in terms of the number of goal scores. This situation explains the fact that the players doing their job professionally.

There is not a significant difference in the total number of yellow card. The number of yellow cards shown in the matches watched by women and children fans was lesser up to 11. The violations leading a player to be shown a yellow card are; being guilty of an unsporting behavior, objecting to the referee's decisions, affecting the the referee's authority, and failing in complying with the sanction arisen as a result of the rules of the game.

As a result, we can say that less yellow cards are shown in the matches played with the attendance of women and children fans, and consequently, matches are played in a more sportsmanlike environment and in accordance with the principles of Fair Play. The fact is seen that children pay more attention to the principle of "fair play and honest behavior" in the matches watched by women and children fans.

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